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The acquisition by students of chemical knowledge that serves the development of society at educational stages occurs during the implementation of chemical education. Formative and standardizing instruments of chemical education include the specialization of general, secondary specialized vocational education, the State educational standard and curriculum, the natural sciences program and textbooks. The state educational standard determines the limits of chemical knowledge, skills and competencies that students can acquire, professional factors and subjects that contribute to the development of society and the acquisition of chemical knowledge, and reflects their chosen specialty in the curriculum included in the educational program. DTS.

The scientific program outlines the fundamentals and scope of chemical knowledge necessary to obtain the chosen specialty in chemistry. In the implementation of chemical education, the chemistry textbook is the main teaching aid. Therefore, the most important task is to write a chemistry textbook perfectly, with a sense of responsibility to society. Below are the didactic requirements for the assignment, formation and content of a chemistry textbook, the standard for the volume and complexity of educational materials, as well as the didactic units of teaching chemistry, the school chemistry course and education that forms the basis of chemical education. Let us dwell on the issues of creating the content of chemical sciences in stages.

Chemistry, like other academic subjects, shapes the personality of students committed to the ideas of independence and equips them with the basics of chemical education. It performs educational and educational -developmental training tasks. The main objectives of studying chemistry are the following:

1. Ensures students' conscious mastery of the principles and methods of chemistry.
2. Forms a scientific worldview among students.
3. By describing the chemical and natural reserves of the republic and the production of products from them related to the topics taught, students will develop loyalty to the Motherland, interest in science and respect for nature.
4. Develops students' activity and thinking when mastering chemical knowledge.
5. Explaining the importance of chemical production in the national economy and production technology, forms the labor education of students and implements issues of introduction to the chemical profession.

It is known that textbooks are the basis of chemical education. It is written on the basis of a program approved by the ministry. The topics covered in the textbook must be consistent with the curriculum. Chemistry is taught based on the topics described in the textbook. The following requirements are imposed for teaching chemistry:

- 1) system of scientific knowledge;
- 2) system of skills and qualifications;
- 3) the experience of creative activity accumulated by humanity in the field of chemistry;
- 4) attitude towards the material world and the environment.

All this is interconnected. For example, it is impossible to carry out chemical reactions without knowing the laws of transition. Without experience, it is impossible to obtain complete knowledge about the object being studied. It is also difficult to master knowledge without

working with textbooks. If a person does not have experience in creative activity, he will not have original ideas. In this case, the teacher becomes an imitator. Because of this, he cannot solve complex problems and connect his knowledge to new conditions. Without creative activity it is difficult to master knowledge and skills. In this case, he cannot correlate his knowledge with life. First, let's look at the system of chemical knowledge in a school chemistry course. The system of scientific knowledge is a complex problem in school chemical education. It is necessary to select such knowledge from scientific data so that in the future it has an unchanged, vital, educational content. The first requirement for the content of a school chemistry course is its scientific nature. The principle of science is based on the theory and laws of processes that reflect the clarification of the identified properties of substances in a logical connection in the content of training.

List of used literature

1. Pak M.S., Bondarenko D.K. Didactic material in teaching chemistry. -SPb: (Osipova), 2013 - 45 p.
2. Kuzurman V.A., Zadorozhny I.V. Methods of teaching chemistry. -Vladimir :(VLDU), 2017 – 88 p.
3. Serbis Takayochta , Dara Leibsil . Using graphic organizers in teaching and learning. (Castello Print Navan), SLSS 2008. 64 pp .
4. Teaching Chemistry - Study Guide Practical Guide and Textbook for Student Teachers, Trainees and Teachers 2013.1 page 34
5. Starichenko B.E. Processing and presentation of pedagogical research data using a computer. Educational and methodological manual. Ural . g os. ped . univ. –Ekaterinburg, 2004. – 218 p.
6. Tolipova Zh.O., Gofurov A.T. Biology ŷkitish techniques. – T.: 2012. – 128 b.
7. Kisrieva F. _ U. _ Formation of key competencies of junior schoolchildren in innovative activities: abstract of thesis. kan . ped . Sci. - Makhachkala , 2012. – 22 p.
8. Pryamikova E.V. Competence-based approach in the modern educational space: functional and structural content: abstract .d is.doc . social Sci. - Ekaterinburg, 2012. – 43 p.